

Maximum Reaction Product Uncertainty and Factorial Schemes in Statistical Mechanics

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In previous notes, we have discussed a method of obtaining equilibrium distributions by balancing reaction probabilities, i.e. taking the \ln (log) of a balance equation and linking it (up to constants) to conservation of energy $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. We have also linked such a scenario to factorial schemes $M! / [m_1! M_2! \dots]$ ((1)) subject to energy and number constraints. In a recent note (1), we argued that reaction balance for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case is based on complete uncertainty of reaction products for each reaction $e_1+e_2=E$. In this note, we try to link this idea of uncertainty of reaction products to the factorial scheme ((1)). For more general cases, $f(e_i)$ is replaced by $g(f(e_i))$ which obeys Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics and yields results for non-Maxwell-Boltzmann $f(e_i)$ such as Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases.

Reaction Balance

In previous notes, we argued that for every $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ ((2a)): $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ ((2b)) for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. One may then take \ln of ((2b)) and link it to ((2a)) yielding: $f(e_i)=\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$ ((3)). This in turn indicates that each $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ for which $e_i+e_j=e$ is the equivalent, thus uncertainty of reaction products is maximized.

We wish to consider a slightly different approach here. Consider the probability for a reaction with conservation of energy to be $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ as above, but insist on uncertainty of reaction products. In such a case:

$$f(a)f(E-a) = f(a+d) f(E-a-d) \quad \text{where } d \text{ is infinitesimal} \quad ((4))$$

The plus and minus d values indicate conservation of energy. ((4)) immediately yields the MB distribution i.e.

$$f(a)f(E-a) = f(a)f(E-a) [1+d \frac{d}{de} \ln(f) \text{ at } a] [1 - d \frac{d}{de} \ln(f) \text{ at } (E-a)]$$

Thus: $d/de \ln(f)$ must be independent of energy, or $f(e)=\exp(-(e-u)/T)$.

This approach does not require taking \ln and equating to a conservation equation as is often done in the literature.

Factorial Schemes

In statistical mechanics, one often sees the maximization problem:

$$d/dm_i \ln\{ M! / [m_1! M_2! \dots] \} + d/dm_i \sum \text{over } i \ m_i e_i + d/dm_i \sum \text{over } i \ m_i \quad ((5))$$

Stirling's approximation is applied to $m_i!$ to replace it with $m_i \ln(m_i)$. Then, one may maximize and obtain $m_i = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$. ((5)) implies one maximizes arrangements subject to constraints on total energy and total particle number. In a previous note, we argued ((5)) really represents a mapping of a gas into a line, with adjacent "particles" reacting i.e. if an m_1 particle were adjacent to an m_3 one, one would have the reaction $m_1 + m_3$. The solution $m_i = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ is such that for every $e_i + e_j = E$, the probability to find e_i next to e_j is $P(e_i)P(e_j)$ or $m_i m_j = \exp(-E/T) \exp(-2u/T)$. Thus, for every e_1 followed by an e_2 ($e_1 + e_2 = E$) one may find an equal number of e_j next to e_j for $e_i + e_j = E$. Thus, there is complete uncertainty in which e_i and e_j come together in an "E" reaction as well as complete uncertainty in the outcome (as long as $e_i + e_j = E$).

In this note, we consider ((5)) in a slightly different manner which does not involve the maximization derivative process. Consider:

$$\{M! / [m_1! m_2! m_3! \dots]\} \quad ((6))$$

Next, consider a particular reaction (this can be any reaction) such that an e_1 particle (associated with m_1) collides with an e_2 (associated with m_2) yielding an e_3 and an e_4 such that $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. Then, energy and particle number are conserved. Thus, ((6)) should not change if one has achieved a maximum. Then:

$$m_1! m_2! m_3! m_4! = (m_1 - 1)! (m_2 - 1)! (m_3 + 1)! (m_4 + 1)! \quad ((7a))$$

Or $m_1 m_2 = (m_3 + 1) (m_4 + 1)$ ((7b)) which is almost the reaction balance result. For the case of large m_i , $m_i + 1 \approx m_i$. One may also consider the reverse reaction $e_3 + e_4 = e_1 + e_2$ which yields:

$(m_1 + 1) (m_2 + 1) = m_3 m_4$ ((7b)) so, to leading order, $m_1 m_2 = m_3 m_4$, but this is an approximation.

The above may be applied to any reaction. ((7b)) then leads to $m_i = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$.

Small Number Factorial Maximization

In the above section, we consider maximization without derivatives with respect to m_i or $d/df(e_i)$. If one uses Stirling's approximation (which drops terms) one does not have the m_i versus $m_i + 1$ issue. For small particle number, however, the issue also appears:

$$\ln(S) = \ln(M!) - \text{Sum over } i \ln(m_i!)$$

So $\ln[(m_i + 1)!] - \ln(m_i!) = \ln(m_i + 1)$ is used to approximate the derivative with respect to m_i for small m_i .

In general, the result should be $\ln(m_i)$ not $\ln(m_i+1)$, so there are some “graininess” issues linked to the factorial scheme. Nevertheless, for large m_i , it appears to yield results.

Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Cases

The above discussion may be applied to Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases to provide a factorial scheme which matches the reaction balance case. The result seems to be:

$$M! \left\{ \text{Product over } i \ (m_i+1)! \right\} / \left[\text{Product over } i \ m_i! \right] \quad ((8))$$

Again one considers a reaction $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ such that:

$$\frac{(m_1+1)! (m_2+1)! (m_3+1)! (m_4+1)!}{[m_1! m_2! m_3! m_4!]} = \frac{m_1! m_2! (m_3+2)! (m_4+2)!}{[(m_1-1)! (m_2-1)! (m_3+1)! (m_4+1)!]}$$

Or

$$(m_1+1)(m_2+1) / [m_1 m_2] = (m_3+2) (m_4+2) / [(m_3+1) (m_4+1)] \quad ((9a))$$

Reversing the reaction yields:

$$(m_1+2) (m_2+2) / [(m_1+1)(m_2+1)] = (m_3+1) (m_4+1) / [m_3 m_4] \quad ((9b))$$

From ((9a)), the correction term obtained by expanding about m_i+1 in the numerators and m_i in the denominator is (because this seems to be where the deviations enter) seems to be:

$(m_3+1)(m_4+1)/[m_3 m_4] \{ -1/m_3 -1/m_4 \} + (m_4+m_3+3)/[m_3 m_4]$ which is roughly the order of $1/m_3$ or $1/m_4$ (whichever is the largest). Thus, as an approximation, one has:

$$(m_1+1)(m_2+1) / [m_1 m_2] = (m_3+1)(m_4+1) / [m_3 m_4] \quad ((10))$$

which in turn leads to the Bose-Einstein distribution.

It seems, however, that the factorial scheme only works for the large m_i case. The idea of uncertainty in reaction products and reaction balance, however, should work for small number cases, although in such a case one might not want to use $m_i=f(e_i)$ which is an average, but consider each possible reaction type.

g(f) Approach

From the factorial approach applied to bosons, one sees that (10) is like a Maxwell-Boltzmann equation for the entities $m_i / (1+m_i) = g(m_i)$. Thus, one may treat $g(m_i)$ as Maxwell-Boltzmann type particles and use the factorial scheme for the MB case i.e.:

$$M! / [m_1! m_2! \dots]$$

This leads to $g(m_i) = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$.

Application of Factorial Schemes

One may ask why factorial schemes are emphasized so much. It seems they are intricately linked to entropy which, in turn, is linked to the grand partition function. The grand partition function is used to calculate fluctuations among other things. Thus, much of the “physics” in a statistical mechanics problem follows from the “entropy” which is an approximation of the factorial scheme used. For example for bosons, we have used a factorial scheme $(m_i+1)!/(m_i!)$ which, using Stirling’s approximation, becomes $-m_i \ln(m_i) + (m_i+1) \ln(m_i+1)$, which is exactly the boson entropy appearing in statistical mechanics texts (2), which in turn leads to $-T \ln$ of the grand canonical partition function using: $E - TS - uN$. Understanding to what degree the factorial scheme holds and how it is linked to reaction balance, may help show to what extent grand canonical partition function results are meaningful.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to examine the idea of reaction balance with uncertainty of reaction products and compare it to maximization schemes for factorial schemes. It seems that factorial schemes are at best a kind of mapping of reaction balance and only apply for large particle numbers.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Information and Reaction Balance in Statistical Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2020)
2. Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1983) page 184.